

RURAL BANDITRY AND WELL-BEING OF WOMEN IN LOGO LOCAL GOVERNMENT OF BENUE STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The murder of men and rape of women during bandit attacks leaves a vacuum in families and communities, as women often serve as caregivers and key contributors to household and community wellbeing. This study investigated rural banditry and well-being of women in Logo Local Government of Benue state Nigeria. The specific objective of the study is to examine the relationship between rape and well-being of women as well as the relationship between murder and the mental health of women in the study area. Extant literature was reviewed based on the variable of study. The correlational survey design was used and Taro Yamene sample technique was used to draw 200 samples for the study. Both qualitative and quantitative instruments were used for collection of data and were statistically analysed. The study therefore concluded that structural violence intersected with traditional vulnerability to the suffering of rural women and health consequences of banditry on rural women. Based on the findings, it was recommended that: Government, in collaboration with local leaders, should strengthen community vigilante groups with appropriate training and non-lethal equipment to enhance surveillance and early warning systems against bandit attacks. Government and NGOs should provide accessible trauma counselling and mental health support for survivors of rape, loss, and community violence.

KEY WORD: Community invasion, banditry. Rape, murder, well-being.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Rural banditry has emerged as one of the most pressing security challenges in Nigeria, particularly in the Middle Belt region, where agrarian communities often experience attacks that disrupt their socioeconomic and health systems. Rural banditry is often characterized by organized violent crimes, including armed robbery, kidnapping, livestock rustling, and arson, carried out by groups within rural communities. These acts are frequently motivated by economic hardship, resource competition, and political instability (Bello, 2018). In Benue State, rural banditry has been exacerbated by historical conflicts over land and grazing rights, leading to frequent clashes between farmers and herders. Logo Local Government Area, a predominantly agrarian community, has borne the brunt of these conflicts, with women often

being the primary victims of banditry due to their vulnerability and roles in community and family settings. (Abdulazeez, 2021).

1.2 Statement of the problem

Rural banditry has emerged as a significant threat to the well-being and socio-economic stability of rural communities in Nigeria, particularly in Logo Local Government Area (LGA) of Benue State. The persistent activities of bandits, including cattle rustling, kidnapping, armed robbery, and violent attacks, have not only disrupted agricultural productivity but have also exacerbated the vulnerability of women to physical, psychological, and socio-economic challenges. Women in rural areas, who are often the backbone of household sustenance and agricultural labor, bear a disproportionate burden of the adverse effects of banditry.

One critical aspect of this problem is the health and well-being of women, which has been severely undermined by the consequences of banditry. Women face direct physical harm during bandit attacks, which often result in injuries, sexual violence, or loss of life. These violent encounters leave lasting physical and psychological scars, with many victims suffering from post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), depression, and anxiety. The lack of adequate healthcare facilities in rural areas compounds the problem, as women are unable to access timely medical attention for injuries sustained during such incidents or for addressing the long-term mental health effects of the violence. Despite the growing recognition of rural banditry as a national security and development issue, there has been insufficient attention paid to its gender-specific impacts, particularly on the health and well-being of women. Policy responses and intervention programmes often focus on security measures and agricultural recovery, with limited efforts to address the immediate and long-term health needs of women affected by banditry that inform this study on rural banditry and health wellbeing of women in Local Government Area of Benue State.

1.3 Research questions

The study sought to find answers to the following research questions:

What is the relationship between rape and wellbeing (Reproductive health) of women in Logo Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria?

What is the relationship between murder and wellbeing (mental health) of women in Logo Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria?

1.4 Objectives of the study

The broad aim of this study was to examine rural banditry and wellbeing of women in Logo Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria. Specifically, this study sought to:

Find out the relationship between rape and wellbeing (Reproductive health) of women in Logo Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria.

Ascertain the relationship between murder and wellbeing (mental health) of women in Logo Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria.

1.5 Statement of hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study

There is no significant relationship between rape and well-being (Reproductive health) of women in Logo Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria.

There is no significant relationship between murder and wellbeing (mental health) of women in Logo Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria.

1.6 Significance of the study

The significance of this study will be of great benefit to women, policymakers, health workers, academic, policy, and societal generally.

The study will benefit the women because the study will raise awareness of the need for community-based support systems and initiatives to empower women. The study will also emphasize the importance of resilience-building measures, such as education and advocacy programmes, to mitigate the long-term effects of banditry on women's health and overall well-being. The study will provide practical insights for healthcare providers, enabling them to develop strategies to address the health needs of women impacted by rural banditry. By identifying specific health challenges, such as increased exposure to violence and limited access to medical care, the study will inform the development of mobile clinics, trauma care programs, and other tailored interventions

1.7 Definition of terms

Community invasion: In this study, community invasion involves the illegal intrusion into a community or settlement. Perpetrators may engage in looting, violence, or other criminal acts during the invasion. The invasion disrupts the peace and security of the affected community.

Wellbeing: In context of this study, health wellbeing refers to injuries, psychological distress, including anxiety, breakdown of community cohesion and death of individuals and communities affected by rural.

Rape: In this study, it refers to a situation whereby bandits forceable have sex with women and girls in the cause of their attacks on communities.

Rural banditry: Rural banditry for the purpose of this study should be seen as the practice of raiding and attacking victims by members of an armed group, whether or not premeditated, using weapons of offence or defense especially in semi-organized groups for the purpose of overpowering the victim and obtaining loot or achieving some social, economic and political goals.

2.1 Literature review

2.1.1 Rape and wellbeing of women

Rape, a pervasive form of gender-based violence, continues to pose significant threats to the health and well-being of women globally. Defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as “physically forced or otherwise coerced penetration of the vulva or anus, using a penis, other body parts or an object,” rape has both immediate and long-term consequences on victims' physical, psychological, reproductive, and social health (WHO, 2013). Contemporary research over the last decade has intensified focus on the multifaceted health impacts of rape on women, revealing a complex interplay between trauma, health outcomes, and access to care. Physical injuries remain a prominent and immediate health outcome of rape. According to Campbell et al. (2014), women who experience sexual violence often sustain genital injuries,

bruises, lacerations, and other forms of bodily harm requiring urgent medical attention. Beyond physical wounds, rape increases the risk of sexually transmitted infections (STIs), including HIV/AIDS. A meta-analysis by Jewkes et al. (2015) established a strong correlation between rape and heightened vulnerability to HIV infection, especially in sub-Saharan Africa, where rape is sometimes used as a weapon of war.

(Khosla et al., 2015). The psychological toll of rape is profound and enduring. Numerous studies highlight an increased prevalence of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), depression, anxiety, and suicidal ideation among rape survivors. For instance, Dworkin et al. (2017) found that nearly 50% of women who experienced rape met the diagnostic criteria for PTSD within a year following the assault. Additionally, chronic stress responses and sleep disturbances are commonly reported, negatively affecting survivors' daily functioning and quality of life (Bryant-Davis et al., 2015). A longitudinal study by Dekel et al. (2019) revealed that women who experience sexual violence during adolescence or adulthood may transmit trauma-related symptoms to their children, either through biological stress pathways or parenting behaviors shaped by unresolved trauma.

Rape also undermines women's social and economic well-being. Survivors frequently encounter stigma, victim-blaming, and ostracism from their families and communities. According to a study by Munala and Maina (2018) in Kenya, societal stigma discouraged many women from reporting rape or seeking healthcare services, leading to untreated health complications and further isolation. Stigma not only limits access to care but also exacerbates psychological distress, as women are made to feel culpable for their victimization (Kalra & Bhugra, 2013). Economically, the consequences of rape include job loss, reduced work productivity, and increased healthcare expenditures. In a U.S.-based study, Peterson et al. (2017) estimated the lifetime cost of rape per female victim at approximately \$122,461, considering medical, legal, and lost productivity costs. Such financial burdens deepen socioeconomic inequalities and hinder survivors' ability to achieve economic independence. According to Choudhry et al. (2020), health professionals often lack training on how to appropriately manage and support survivors of sexual violence, resulting in secondary victimization within healthcare settings. Furthermore, comprehensive care encompassing forensic examination, STI prophylaxis, mental health counseling, and legal support is often fragmented or inaccessible, especially in low-resource settings (Leone et al., 2020). Innovative models, such as one-stop crisis centers, have been implemented in some countries to address these gaps by integrating medical, psychological, and legal services in a single location. Evaluations of such centers in Malaysia and South Africa show improved uptake of services and better health outcomes for survivors (Kim & Motsei, 2017). However, scaling up such models requires political will, funding, and cross-sectoral collaboration.

2.1.2 Murder and health wellbeing of women

The effects of the nomadic influx and rural banditry can be categorized into humanitarian, economic, social, and security impacts. First, these issues lead to humanitarian crises, including loss of life, injuries, and forced displacements. Research has shown that the nomadic influx and rural banditry increasingly involve physical force and violence, often resulting in deaths and severe injuries. A study by Aréen (2023) in Kenya examined the role of small arms and light weapons in conflicts between farmers and herders. The study found that the historical conflict

between the Pokot and Turkana has experienced significant violence, with notable escalations such as in 2015. Sporadic clashes linked to cattle raids over territory, water access, and local boundaries occurred in 2013 and 2015 (Uppsala Conflict Data Programme UCDP, 2022). After an attack in November 2014 that resulted in around 20 police officers dead in the border area between Baringo and Turkana counties, a military operation was launched to search for attackers and disarm raiders. In 2015, retaliatory raids and counter-raids between the Pokot and Turkana led to over 50 deaths in the most violent incident (UCDP, 2022). Between 2011 and 2021, UCDP (2022) reported 261 fatalities. The widespread presence of automatic weapons in the area is one of the reasons for the escalation of violence between the Pokot and Turkana (UCDP, 2022).

Ahmed (2022) conducted a study on the conflicts between farmers and herders in northern Ghana, focusing on the impact of climate change and the policy responses in place. The research highlighted significant incidents in 2016, 2013, and 2019, during which young men in Gushegu, armed with machetes, attacked Fulani herders. These attacks led to numerous deaths, the burning of homes, loss of property, and cattle theft. Fulton and Nickels (2017) explored how Islamic terrorist groups in the Sahel and Sahara regions are exploiting the grievances of pastoralists, predominantly Muslim, to garner support for their agendas. They noted that conflicts between farmers and Fulani herders have long existed in West Africa, predating the rise of terrorism in the area. The study estimated that around 60,000 people have died in pastoralist-related conflicts since 2001, attributing these conflicts to structural violence stemming from marginalization, discrimination, and unequal access to resources like pastureland and water. This situation breeds frustration and increases grievances. The research cited the ongoing conflicts in Nigeria, where the government grants preferential land rights to indigenous people, marginalizing settlers, including herders. The 2001 Pastoral Charter of Mali, which aimed to resolve disputes between farmers and herders, was also mentioned as favoring sedentary farmers to the detriment of herders.

In a study by Lenshie and Jacob (2020) on nomadic migration and rural violence in Nigeria, it was found that Fulani herders had attacked several villages in Taraba State, resulting in numerous deaths, burnt houses, and many displaced persons. Similar incidents occurred in Ardo-Kola, Bali, Donga, and Gassol LGAs. This conflict between Fulani herders and farmers in Taraba, an agrarian state, raises concerns about food insecurity not only in Taraba but also in other northeastern states relying on its food supply. Amnesty International reported that at least 1,813 people were killed across 17 states in 2018, almost doubling the 894 deaths in 2017 (International Crisis Group, 2017). These deaths were attributed to conflicts between Fulani herders and farmers, Boko Haram attacks, and armed banditry. The Nigerian government has been criticized for failing to hold perpetrators accountable, thus exacerbating the insecurity (Channels Television, 2018). According to Fajonyomi et al. (2016), the government's lack of proactive response has contributed to the violence perpetrated by Fulani herders. These researchers noted that farmers believe nomadic herders bribe government officials and traditional rulers to influence judgments in their favor.

2.2 Theoretical Frame

2.2.1 Situational Action Theory

Situational Action Theory (SAT) is a theory of crime developed in 2004 by Per-Olof Wikström. Situational Action Theory (SAT) is a criminological theory that focuses on the

role of situations in influencing human behaviour, particularly criminal behaviour. When applying SAT to the context of nomadic influx and rural banditry in the North-central region of Nigeria, several assumptions guide the analysis:

Situational variation: SAT assumes that criminal behaviour is influenced by the specific situations individuals encounter. In the context of nomadic influx and rural banditry, the theory suggests that the dynamics of these situations, such as access to resources, environmental conditions, and social interactions, play a crucial role in influencing criminal actions.

The theory is relevant to this study because, by understanding the situational factors influencing nomadic influx and rural banditry, policymakers can develop targeted interventions to alter the situational dynamics. This might involve improving economic opportunities, enhancing law enforcement capabilities, or implementing community-based programmes. SAT provides a basis for designing crime prevention strategies that focus on altering the situational elements conducive to nomadic influx and rural banditry. This could include efforts to improve security infrastructure, enhance community policing, and address the root causes of criminal motivations.

Consideration of situational elements supports the design of environments that discourage criminal behaviour. This might involve planning and designing settlements in a way that minimizes opportunities for banditry and reduces tensions between nomadic and settled communities. SAT emphasizes the importance of social interactions in shaping behavior. Applied to nomadic influx and rural banditry, community engagement programs can be developed to foster positive social interactions, promote understanding between nomadic and settled communities, and build a sense of collective responsibility for security. In conclusion, Situational Action Theory provides a valuable framework for analyzing the complex dynamics of nomadic influx and rural banditry in the North-central region of Nigeria, offering insights that can inform targeted interventions and crime prevention strategies.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

Correlation research design was used for this study. Correlation research is a type of non-experimental research method in which a researcher measures two variables, understands and assesses the statistical relationship between them with no influence from any extraneous variable

3.2 Population of the study

The population of the study will be 244,800 people of Logo Local Government Area consisting of adult (18+ years of ages) residing in the areas (Projected National Population Commission, 2022).

3.3 Sample size

The sample size for this study will be 200. The sample of 200 was determined by Taro-Yamane (1967). According to Wimmer & Domincik (2011), we can determine size from heterogeneous population using Taro-Yamane's (1967) give as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where

n = the sample size required

N = the population size

E = level of confidence (0.05)

$$\text{Hence: } n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

$$\frac{122,400}{1+122,400 (0.05)^2}$$

$$\frac{122,400}{1+312,200 \times 0.0025}$$

$$\frac{122,400}{313}$$

$$n = 199.347$$

$$n = 200$$

3.4 Sampling techniques

Multi-stage sampling is effective for selecting respondents across different administrative Council wards divisions. First, purposive sampling will be used to select Gaambe, Mbagber, Turan and Tswarev because the council wards and communities are most affected by rural banditry based on security reports and local government records. Secondly, systematic random sampling to select 200 women of reproductive age as respondents within the identified council wards or communities.

3.5 Source of data

Data used in this study was collected through primary and secondary sources. The primary sources consisted of first-hand information that was obtained from respondents during fieldwork. Also, questionnaire as well as key informant interview was part of the data collection. The unstructured interview will give the interviewee the opportunity to state his/her opinion on the research questions. The secondary sources of data include textbooks, journals articles, internet materials, national population reports, reports of dailies, gazette materials among others.

3.6 Instrument for data collection

The questionnaire was adopted for data collection. The questionnaire consisted of 20 items, and it was titled "Questionnaire on Cross-Rural Banditry and Health-Wellbeing of Women (RBHWW)". The questionnaire was divided into two units. Section A, was to elicit information on the respondents personal demography such as sex, age, marital status, educational level and occupation. Section B, consisted of 16 items designed to measure rape, community invasion and murder; each requires respondents to indicate the frequency of their responses on a high, moderate, and low.

3.7 Method of data coding

Data collected was edited, coded, and analysed using presentation and analysis methods. Frequency distribution, simple percentages and simple linear regression analysis procedure was used in analysing the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

3.8 Method of data analysis

Descriptive and inferential statistics was used for data analysis. Descriptive statistic such as simple percentages, tables and frequency was used demographic characteristics of the respondents while inferential statistic such as simple linear regression was used to test the hypotheses.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 General description of variables

Under this heading, the researcher presented and analyzed the data collected on sex, age, marital status, educational level and occupation.

4.1.1 Data presentation

Table 4.1: Demographic distribution of respondents

Demographic Attribute	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age		
18-30yrs	64	32.3
31-45yrs	59	29.5
46-60yrs	59	29.5
61yrs and above	35	8.8
Total	200	100
Marital Status		
Single	83	41.5
Married	62	30.5
Divorced	27	13.8
Separated	8	4.0
Widow/widower	21	10.3
Total	200	100
Primary		
Primary	54	27.0
Secondary	85	42.3
Tertiary	61	30.8
Total	200	100
Occupation		
Civil and Public Servant	29	7.2
Farming	52	26.0
Trading	52	26.8
Artisan	40	19.8
Unemployed	40	20.3
Total	200	100
Total	200	100

Source: Field survey, 2025

Table 1 below showed that that 107 representing 51.7% of the (200) respondents were males while 48.3% (193) were females. Table 4.1 was categorized into age groups. It was observe that out of the 400 respondents, 32.3% were 18-30 years, 29.5% were between the ages of 31-45, 29.5% were between the age brackets of 46-60 years, and 8.8% were above 61 years. In marital status, 30.5 % (61) were single, 41.5% (83) were married, divorce had 13% (55), while 8 (4.0%) were separated, and 41 (10.3%) were widow/widowers. The same table 4.1 above shows that, out of the 200 respondents, 27.0% (54) had primary education, while 42.3% had secondary education, and 30.8% tertiary education (such as OND/NCE, HND/B.Sc, Master Degree had master Degree and others educational qualifications.

Under the occupational distribution of the respondents, it was discovered that, 7.2% (29) were civil and public servants, 26.0% (52) were farming, 26.8% (53) were trading, 19.8% were artisan and 41 (20.3%) were unemployed.

4.2 Presentation of results

Hypothesis one

There is no significant relationship between rape and wellbeing (reproductive health) of women in Logo Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria. The independent variable in this study is rape while dependent variable is health wellbeing of women. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to test the hypothesis and the result presented in table 2.

TABLE 2

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient of the relationship between rape and wellbeing (reproductive health) of women in Logo Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria.

Variable	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	p-level
Rape X	200	7.96	3.76	0.261	0.05
Health wellbeing Y	200	7.59	3.35		

*Significant at .05, r-Critical= 0.088, R2 =0.321

Results

The result as presented in table 1 ($r=0.261$, $p=.000$) indicated that there is significance relationship between rape and health wellbeing of women in Logo Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected at 0.05 level of significance and the alternate hypothesis was retained. The result also shows R2 of 0.321 which indicates that rape accounted for 26.1% of the health wellbeing of women in Logo Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria

Hypothesis two

There is no significant relationship between murder and wellbeing (meatal health) of women in Logo Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria. The independent variable in this study is murder while dependent variable is health wellbeing of women. Pearson Product

Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to test the hypothesis and the result presented in table 3.

TABLE 3

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient of the relationship between murder and wellbeing (mental health) of women in Logo Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria

Variable	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	p-level
Murder X	200	7.66	3.67	0.432	.000
Health wellbeing Y	200	8.33	4.22		

*Significant at .05, r-Critical= 0.088, R2 =0.187

Results

The result as presented in table 3 ($r=0.432$, $p=.000$) indicated there is a significant relationship between murder and health wellbeing of women in Logo Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected at 0.05 level of significance and the alternate hypothesis was retained. The result also shows R2 of 0.187 which indicates that murder accounted for 18.7% of the health wellbeing of women in Logo Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria

4.3 Discussion of findings

The result of first hypothesis revealed that there is significance relationship between rape and wellbeing of women in Logo Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria. The finding is in agreement with study of A study by World Health Organization (WHO, 2021) highlights that rape is strongly associated with adverse reproductive outcomes, including unwanted pregnancies, unsafe abortions, and sexually transmitted infections (STIs), including HIV. In their multicountry study, survivors reported increased gynecological complications and lower reproductive autonomy. Similarly, Oladipo and Balogun (2018), found that victims of rape often suffer physical injuries, including genital trauma and chronic pelvic pain. Their research also recorded increased cases of post-rape pregnancies and complications arising from unsafe abortion practices among adolescent girls in urban slums.

Findings from last hypothesis revealed that there is significant relationship between murder and health wellbeing of women in Logo Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria. This finding agreed with that of Abrahams et al. (2014) found that beyond the fatal outcome, women in violent relationships often experience chronic psychological stress, depression, and a diminished quality of life, which deteriorates their health wellbeing long before their lives are ultimately taken. Also, Dawson and Carrigan (2021) emphasize the mental health impact on children and families of murdered women. Their study notes that daughters of murdered mothers are at a higher risk of depression and suicide, thereby extending the impact of such violence across generations.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of the study

This study examined rural banditry and wellbeing of women in Logo Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria. Review of literature was based on the variables of the study.

Situational Action Theory was used to discuss the variables and the correlational research design was adopted. A sample 200 respondents were adopted using the Taro Yamani sample size determination technique for the study. The study relied on primary and secondary sources of data collection. Instruments of data collection was the questionnaire, before disturbing to respondents, the instruments were pass face and content validity. A section was dedication, data presentation, analysis and discussion of findings.

5.2 Conclusion

The study of rural banditry and its impact on the health and wellbeing of women in Logo Local Government Area of Benue State reveals a disturbing intersection between insecurity and gendered vulnerability. Rape, as a weapon of violence, inflicts deep trauma, often leading to long-term mental health issues, sexually transmitted infections, and social stigmatization. Community invasions have led to mass displacements, destruction of homes, and loss of livelihoods, thereby increasing women's exposure to hunger, homelessness, and disease. Furthermore, the targeted or incidental murder of women and family members results in psychological distress, grief, and a breakdown of familial and community support structures.

This research adds to the growing body of literature on the gendered impacts of rural insecurity by focusing specifically on the health consequences of rural banditry on women in Logo Local Government Area. It highlights how structural violence intersects with traditional vulnerabilities to amplify the suffering of rural women. The study also contributes empirical evidence that can inform public health policy, conflict mitigation strategies, and humanitarian interventions in conflict-prone rural settings.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

Government and NGOs should provide accessible trauma counselling and mental health support for survivors of rape, loss, and community violence.

Existing laws on gender-based violence should be fully enforced, and perpetrators of rape and murder during community invasions must be swiftly prosecuted.

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